

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 4.7

Demo 3: Forest and habitat monitoring using innovative technologies II

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This deliverable describes the follow up to the initial action plans and engagement strategies for the LandSense demonstration pilots in Spain and Indonesia, including the improvements and modifications in the Natura Alert tools as well as some of the results achieved in 2019 and at the beginning of 2020.
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List of Acronyms

BLI	BirdLife International
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
DPMS	Badan Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Desa (Village Community Empowerment Body)
EEA	European Environment Agency
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
IBA	Important Bird and Biodiversity Area
IBAT	Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool
KBA	Key Biodiversity Site
LCGs	Local Conservation Groups
LULC	Land Use and Land Cover
N2000	Natura 2000 site
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SPAs	Special Protection Areas
SCI/SAC	Sites of Community Importance /Special Areas of Conservation

1 Introduction

Since the late 1970s, the BirdLife Partnership has been working collectively to identify, document and protect places on the Earth with the greatest significance for the conservation of the world's birds. As a result, over 13,000 Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBAs) have been identified.

However, we lack comprehensive monitoring of the condition of these sites, with an increasing number of IBAs under threat from damaging development – the majority of which appears to be poorly planned and does not take environmental values into account. Sites face a wide range of problems, which require an equally wide range of solutions.

The demonstration cases in Spain and Indonesia show how citizens can be involved in monitoring threats to biodiversity, habitats and people, using tools such as Natura Alert, a mobile and web app that enables citizens to act and report on these sites in order to prevent further damage or loss to these crucial areas. Screenshots from the Natura Alert web app are shown in Figure 1.

The key objectives of these demonstration cases are to:

- ❖ Improve the **monitoring of IBAs, KBAs and Natura 2000 sites** and reduce their degradation
- ❖ **Engage local communities** in habitat monitoring, threat identification and reporting
- ❖ **Empower locals** to participate in the decision making
- ❖ Make **monitoring more cost effective**.

Natura Alert is being tested in Spain and Indonesia, thanks to the volunteer network of two BirdLife partners: SEO/BirdLife and Burung. While the Spanish volunteers are focusing on threats to birds and habitats within IBAs and Natura 2000 sites, the Indonesian communities are validating alerts from satellite-image analysis of forest change on Flores island.

Citizen observations trigger real-time alerts to national and regional IBA/KBA coordinators at BirdLife International, who will ensure that the data are of high quality and produce regional and global monitoring assessments that could help to monitor some indicators from the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).

Also, researchers and practitioners around the globe can benefit from this type of data, as well as institutions and stakeholders from the private sector willing to make better decisions based on high quality data via the Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool (IBAT).

This report describes the main results and challenges of the Habitat and Forest Monitoring pilots.

Figure 1: Screenshots of the Natura Alert web app in Spain and Flores island, Indonesia. Polygons in green are IBAs and KBAs identified by the local partners SEO/BirdLife and Burung.

2 Demonstration Pilots: Scope and approaches

2.1 Spain

In Spain, there are 469 IBAs and 2324 Natura 2000 sites (657 SPAs and 1667 SCI/SAC/pSCI). Monitoring the IBA network is a key challenge for SEO/BirdLife due to limited resources to cover this large number of sites. To address this problem, Natura Alert has been developed within the LandSense Citizen Observatory project. The mobile app and web portal allow users to pinpoint the location of threats to biodiversity and habitat changes, to help prevent further damage or loss to our biodiversity. We are particularly interested in threats that are occurring inside IBAs, Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs) and Natura 2000 sites in the European Union (see Figure 2 for examples from the Natura 2000 Network Viewer), although submitting records in other areas is also possible. Information on the condition of these sites, the threats to them, the conservation measures in place and the changes in these aspects over time are essential to set priorities, hold governments to account and inform policies and decision-makers. Volunteers can share their observations with the wider community and help to map the state of our most valuable sites around the world. They can download the Nature Alert mobile app to quickly record their observations in the field or use the web app to discover more functionalities, such as visualizing reports from other users, creating dashboards per country and downloading their own reports. Figure 3 shows the flows of data captured in Natura Alert for three types of user, i.e., volunteers, IBA caretakers and national coordinators.

Figure 2: Screenshots of the Natura 2000 viewer. The spatial data submitted by each Member State are validated by the European Environment Agency (EEA) and linked to the descriptive data. The boundaries of all the SPAs are integrated into the Natura Alert web app

Figure 3: Data flow in Natura Alert Spain.

2.2 Indonesia

In Indonesia, the LandSense project is being implemented in one of the most beautiful landscapes of Flores Island, i.e., the so-called Mbeliling Landscape (Figure 4). This area consists of preserved forests and community-owned forests. Due to the area's rich biodiversity, it is classified as a Key Biodiversity Area. As the pressure on Mbeliling's forests continues to grow, significant rates of deforestation and forest degradation are occurring. This process is destroying natural habitats, with terrible consequences for forest biodiversity.

The LandSense project is addressing the underlying cause of biodiversity loss by mainstreaming the value of biodiversity across local communities and local governments by enforcing the commitment to conduct community-based forest monitoring.

Figure 4: Community-based monitoring activity in Golo Desat Village, Mbeliling Landscape, Flores

For the first time ever in the Eastern part of Indonesia, the LandSense project is building an innovative citizen observatory for forest and habitat monitoring, by connecting local communities with remote sensing and apps. LandSense is allowing communities to play a key role in forest and habitat monitoring and getting them directly involved in the co-creation of the solution. The results of the monitoring will serve as a valuable input to the village development in the 4 targeted villages (shown in Figure 5), promoting demand-driven policy response and raising village agendas to become a development priority.

Figure 5: Location of the LandSense intervention villages in Flores Island, Indonesia

3 Target Groups

Tables 1 and 2 provide an overview of the target groups in Spain and Flores Island, Indonesia, including their roles and experiences, any barriers to involvement and factors that aid in their participation.

Table 1: Target groups in Spain

SPAIN	
Target group	Role and experiences, barriers, helping factors
National IBA coordinator (SEO/BirdLife staff)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improve the relationships and communication with volunteers, refresh their engagement ▪ Reach a wider audience and recruit new volunteers ▪ Promote SEO’s IBA/Natura 2000 Programme ▪ Significant time savings gained in producing annual reports related to the state of the IBAs thanks to the mobile app and web app.
IBA caretakers (already engaged)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ They will feel they are part of the bigger picture and that they can actively contribute not only in gathering data but also by participating in the workshops and consultations. ▪ They have had the opportunity to co-design the mobile app and web app, so they will feel inspired and motivated to use it. ▪ It will be easier to report back to SEO with the mobile/web app. ▪ They will receive specific training on threat identification
Bird Monitoring Volunteers (already engaged)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Until now, their main focus has been on counting birds, but now they have an exciting opportunity to report threats at the same time, so their volunteered time will be even more valuable ▪ They will receive specific training on threat identification and they can exchange experiences, attend workshops, participate actively in the consultation process, etc.
Other citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nature lovers, outdoor sporty people, biology students, non-bird naturalists, etc., can see an opportunity to participate in a pilot case linked to areas to which they are attached. ▪ Moreover, other BLI partners in Europe can be inspired by LandSense and design their own campaigns to call for citizen action using our mobile app.

Table 2: Target groups in Indonesia

INDONESIA	
Target groups	Role and experiences, barriers, helping factors
Flores IBA Coordinator (Burung Staff)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The IBA Coordinator has worked with the Local Conservation Groups, assisting them in conducting natural resource monitoring • The Flores IBA Coordinator has helped us to connect with the Department of Village Empowerment of West Manggarai • The Flores IBA Coordinator has assisted us in having discussions with village authorities in 4 target villages
Local Conservation Groups (LCGs) at 4 targeted villages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After Burung Indonesia conducted refreshment training on how to conduct community-based natural resource monitoring, the LCGs in 4 villages have stronger willingness to implement natural resource monitoring in their respective villages. This was demonstrated through the increased number of LCG members participating in the monitoring • They are feeling inspired because of the involvement of village authorities in the monitoring activity • They are excited about the technology that will be introduced. This statement was made during the monitoring activity on the ground
Village Authorities at 4 targeted villages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The village authorities in Golo Damu, Liang Ndara, Golo Kondeng and Golo Desat villages have shown good support and involvement in this monitoring activity. Currently, they are drafting a Village Head Decree as a legal basis to integrate the community-based monitoring process into the Village Development Plan. • The Village Head Decree is a written regulation that contains legal binding norms and is formed and/or determined by the village authorized to be aligned with the procedures specified in Indonesian law.
West Manggarai Local Government (Village Empowerment Department and Forest Management Unit)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aligned with LandSense’s objective, the Community and Village Empowerment Agency of West Manggarai has started promoting demand-driven policy responses. • The Forest Management Unit of West Manggarai has agreed to work together with Local Conservation Groups in conducting monitoring in state-forest areas.
Local Communities in 4 targeted villages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The broader communities in Golo Damu, Liang Ndara, Golo Kondeng and Golo Desat villages will be empowered by the village authorities to participate in the monitoring activities. Some of the specific groups such as academics and women groups are being trained to do the monitoring.

4 Engagement strategies

4.1 Spain

In 2019, SEO/BirdLife found synergies between LandSense and a LIFE project called ‘Followers’. The main goal of the ‘Followers’ project is to increase awareness of the Natura 2000 Network and raise awareness of conservation through involvement of a minimum of 300 young volunteers from the European Solidarity Corps. ‘Followers’ gives young volunteers the opportunity to work together with scientists, professionals from the Spanish Ornithological Society, the oldest conservation association in Spain, and other volunteers from all over Europe, which will help expand their cultural and social skills. They are able to acquire new skills that will be useful for their future in the conservation field, such as participating in data collection campaigns related to IBAs, which have played an important role in the designation of the Natura 2000 sites in Spain. Volunteers become familiar with processes to determine the conservation status of the IBAs, which of them are most threatened, and why. Video tutorials to use Natura Alert tools were shared among volunteers and training materials were provided.

In order to sustain their engagement, articles on LandSense progress and IBA/N2000 monitoring were written up in the SEO/BirdLife bulletin and their magazine “Aves y Naturaleza” (Figure 6).

Figure 6: An article about LandSense in the SEO/BirdLife bulletin

In Natura Alert, volunteers can access and manage their observations, as well as to check the state of their observations (verified, approved or not), as shown in Figure 7. They can also check threats happening in their area that have been reported by other users, etc.

Figure 7: User view of “My Reports” in the Natura Alert web app

For more detailed information about the engagement strategies and campaigns in Spain and Indonesia, please see Deliverables 2.2 and 2.3.

4.2 Flores Island, Indonesia

After stakeholder consultation and Local Conservation Groups meeting in 2017, the engagement strategies in 2018 were focused on reinforcing the participation of the local authorities in community-based monitoring through the institutionalization of this monitoring program at the local level.

We have closely engaged the West Manggarai Community and Village Empowerment Agency as the key stakeholder in village development and community engagement. Some of the outcomes were:

- The community-based monitoring results will contribute to data validation for a “technology-based village profile”, which is an online platform to show the potential of the village to relevant stakeholders, including the national government and the business sector.
- The Head of the West Manggarai Community and Village Empowerment Agency is delegating one of his representatives, Mr. Apri, to be involved in the discussions to integrate the monitoring into the Village Development Plan.
- The West Manggarai Community and Village Empowerment Agency will be disseminating the village profile on their website: <https://manggaraibaratkab.go.id>. Based on the discussions, they will be providing some space for showcasing the community-based monitoring initiative and the results.

The project consultations with the Village Authorities in four targeted villages have also delivered a new consensus to incorporate community-based monitoring in the Village Development Program. This means that the village authority will be responsible for the planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of this program as well as providing the funding needed. Moreover, the Local Conservation Groups will also get better recognition because the Village Head will issue a Decree that states the role of LCGs in the monitoring activities. Currently, two of the four villages are in the stage of drafting the Decree and revising their village funds (Liang Ndara and Golo Desat villages). Burung Indonesia is working closely with them to facilitate this process.

Figure 8: Discussion between Burung Indonesia, the Community and Village Empowerment Agency and the Village Authority in Golo Damu Village

Burung Indonesia has worked with these Local Conservation Groups for almost 7 years in West Manggarai. Community-based monitoring is not a new activity in this area, as they have conducted it from 2011 to 2015. However, the monitoring results are still not well documented. We are trying to revive this community-based monitoring activity through LandSense to improve the process and make it more sustainable.

LandSense meetings in the villages, such as the stakeholder consultation (17th May 2017), the meeting with LCGs (17th June 2017), discussions with the BPMS (2nd May 2018) and meetings with 4 targeted village authorities (7th – 9th May 2018) were always conducted in an inclusive manner to empower the village authorities to invite everyone interested in participating, with a special focus on women groups and academics. An example of one of these discussions is shown in Figure 8. Burung is also focusing on capacity development of the Local Conservation Groups in conducting forest and habitat monitoring (Figure 9).

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 9: Community-based monitoring in a) Golo Desat Village (February 2018) b) Golo Kondeng Village (April 2018), c) Liang Ndara Village (May 2018) and d) Golo Damu Village (May 2018).

Steps undertaken to sustain engagement of the users

These steps include:

1. The institutionalization of community-based monitoring in the Village Development Plan, which will make it a legal mandate in which the local authorities and the LCGs will have to work together.
2. Engagement with the West Manggarai Community and Village Empowerment Agency in the utilization of the monitoring data. Through this engagement, the agency will work to ensure the sustainability of the monitoring results.
3. Providing Local heroes awards (ongoing BirdLife International initiative). Burung Indonesia is selecting the candidates for this year.

Steps undertaken to give feedback to the users

The following steps are being undertaken:

4. The Natura Alert mobile app informs users about the state of their observations, threats happening in their area that have been reported by other users, etc. The app will also inform them when they enter a KBA/ IBA.
5. Burung will produce an annual report with the data gathered by the locals and distribute the copies in the villages. Results will be also shared on Burung's website and via social media.
6. The monitoring results will be shared on the website of the West Manggarai Community and Village Empowerment Agency (<https://manggaraibaratkab.go.id>). These data will also feed the Village Development Plan in the 4 targeted villages as well as the proposed program at the regional level.
7. The data collected will be fed into the World Bird & Biodiversity Database.
8. Articles on Burung's magazine will appear.
9. Information will appear on the BirdLife Datazone section for LandSense: <http://datazone.birdlife.org/info/citizenscience/landsense>

5 Main achievements

There have been several achievements in the forest and habitat monitoring pilots as outlined below:

- There have been great improvements to the Natura Alert mobile app and web app <https://natura-alert.net/explore>, which were developed after multiple consultations with different audiences, from experts in on site monitoring to biodiversity volunteers, regular citizens, etc. We managed to find collaborators and testers in Spain, Indonesia, UK, France, Italy, Tunisia, Austria, India, Georgia, Armenia and Greece. Their valuable feedback has been integrated, and improved versions of the app have been released continually over the past year. Both platforms have been translated into English, French, Bahasa and German. Greek is on the way. Results from the first campaign are shown in the Natura Alert web app in Figure 10.
- The workshop in Indonesia (April 2019 – Figure 11) was a success and helped to build a stronger relationship with the partners and local actors, in particular:
 - Active participation of multiple stakeholders: 4 members of the Local Conservation Group, Village Authorities: leader of 4 villages, Government agencies at the district level: Forest Management Unit, Environment Agency, Planning Agency, Nature Reserve Authority, Agriculture Agency.
 - The integration of the forest and habitat monitoring program into the Village Development Plan in 2 of the targeted villages. Authorities will dedicate some funding to support their work.
 - Mobilization of local stakeholders for the first on-the-ground testing of Natura Alert: 30 remote sensing alerts were ground-truthed, and 13 participants produced 140 observations on the ground, taking pictures, videos and adding notes.
- Hundreds of observations were collected on Flores Island thanks to the organization of 4 remote sensing validation campaigns in April/May 2019, August 2019, September 2019 and November 2019 (Figure 12). Data on the location of threats were provided to the remote sensing experts, who produced the alerts to ensure that they use the information to improve their algorithms and the accuracy of the alerts.
- Identified synergies with other projects resulted in more than 200 threat observations in Spain. The LIFE Followers project (European Solidarity Corps) has been using Natura Alert to collect data in the field. Discussions with the Forest Governance project implemented in South East Asia are taking place to assess whether Natura Alert could be used. More information can be found here: <https://www.birdlife.org/worldwide/news/empowering-local-people-better-forest-governance>

Figure 10: Results from the first data collection campaign in Spain. Agricultural expansion and intensification has been the most common threat affecting IBAs (59 sites), followed by Human intrusions and disturbances (40 sites).

Figure 11: The celebration of the Natura Alert technical meeting in Flores, Indonesia, in April 2019, was a great opportunity to meet the main stakeholders (Forest Management Unit, Village & Community Empowerment Agency, Nature Conservation Agency, Burung Indonesia)

Figure 12: Natura Alert training for local stakeholders, August 2019

6 Overview of the Natura Alert mobile app and web app

In October 2019, BirdLife International and IIASA met in Cambridge to improve the technical aspects of Natura Alert and to define a common strategy to ensure the sustainability of the tool.

It was a fruitful meeting where the partners agreed to sign a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) for scientific and technical collaboration beyond 2020, as well as a Licence Agreement for the mobile app and web app. Discussions around the migration of the data hosted by IIASA to BirdLife servers are still ongoing.

6.1 Mobile app

These are the final functionalities of the two mobile app versions (Android and iOS):

- **Record:** A user marks the location of a threat and reports it by choosing one option from a set of buttons or dropdown menus (**threats, severity, scope and timing**) (Figure 13). The different questions are based on the internationally agreed **IBA monitoring form**, which is used worldwide by BirdLife partners to monitor the state of IBAs and Natura 2000 sites.
- **Protected Areas/IBAs/Natura 2000 sites (SPAs):** the user is able to add layers to the base map, i.e., the IBA polygons, the SPA polygons and the satellite view (Figure 14).
- **Profile:** users can visualize all their reported observations and upload them or delete them (Figure 15). This functionality will allow users to **work offline**, since they will be able to store observations when the internet is not available and upload them later when they are connected. Users are also provided with feedback on the total number of reports provided by the Natura Alert community in Spain.

The web app, the API and the data collected are stored on rented Hetzner servers operated by IIASA, while the Natura Alert mobile app is stored in GitHub and released via IIASA's Apple Appstore and Google Playstore accounts.

Figure 13: Screenshots from the Natura Alert app to report a threat

Figure 14: Screenshots from the Natura Alert app showing the IBAs and Natura 2000 sites (SPAs)

Figure 15: Screenshots from the Natura Alert app showing the 'Profile' features

6.2 Web app

Threat data collection (Spain)

In 2019, almost 300 threat observations were gathered in Spain, including the Canary and Balearic Islands. Of these, 86% of the threat observations were reported inside IBAs and 14% outside. Some of the preliminary results show that *Agricultural expansion and intensification* has been the most common threat in IBAs (59 sites), followed by *Human intrusions and disturbances* (40 sites) and *pollution* (35 sites). Outside of the IBAs, the most common threat was *Energy production & mining* (8 sites) and *Residential & commercial development* (7 sites). An example of viewing the data as a chart is shown in Figure 16, while

Figure 17 shows clusters of observations across Spain. Figure 18 shows the details of one observation uploaded by a user.

Figure 16: Screenshot from the Natura Alert web app, Charts section.

Figure 17: Screenshot from Natura Alert web app showing the number of observations as clusters across Spain.

Figure 18: Screenshot from the Natura Alert web app of an example observation uploaded by a user. The comments describe how this new road is crossing/fragmenting a very important habitat for the capercaillie in the Pyrenees (*Tetrao urogallus aquitanicus*).

Regarding the technical developments of the tools in 2019, the efforts were focused on the development of the 'Annual Assessment' functionality. The annual assessment functionality has been built following the IBA monitoring form developed by BirdLife International and used by the BirdLife Partnership across the globe, which is based on the relationship between the state, pressure and response (Figure 19). This could facilitate the engagement of other BirdLife partners in using Natura Alert within their monitoring schemes.

This functionality within Natura Alert (Figure 20) is critical for the IBA caretakers to create a comprehensive report on the state of their IBA(s) using the threat observations sent from other users and their own knowledge of the site. Once they compile the report, they send it to the IBA national coordinator through the platform. This makes the workflow much more effective, as in the past all this work was done manually using paper forms or via email, phone calls, etc.

Figure 19: The relationship between indicators of pressure, state and response.

Figure 20: Screenshots from the Annual Assessment form that is filled in by IBA caretakers and sent to IBA national coordinators once finished.

Ideally, in 2020, the IBA national coordinator in Spain should receive one Annual Assessment report per year per site. This will allow him to prepare the final assessment about the state of the IBA network in Spain.

Validation of remote sensing alerts (Indonesia)

Since April 2019, Burung has undertaken 4 different validation campaigns (April, August, September and November). The alerts were provided by Sinergise, Heidelberg University and Wageningen University (Figure 21). The time series covered different periods between August 2018 and October 2019. As the number of alerts was very high, it was decided to prioritize the alerts based on the following criteria:

- Priority 1=alerts **within KBA and protected forest**
- Priority 2=alerts **within KBA but outside protected forest**
- Priority 3=alerts **outside of KBAs.**

Figure 21: Map that shows the boundaries of the KBAs (pink colour), the protected forests (green areas) and the location of the alerts (yellow box) in order to prioritize the alerts provided by the remote sensing experts.

For example, in the 2nd validation campaign, out of 714 alerts, only 64 were priority 1, 93 alerts were priority 2 and 557 alerts were priority 3. Of the 64 alerts with priority 1, Burung managed to validate 32 of them in 2 field visits. Details are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of the 4 validation campaigns carried out in 2019

Campaign	Field visit for validation	Data provider	Time series	Number of Alerts	Prioritization of alerts	Number of Alerts Validated
1	Apr-19	Sinergise, Heidelberg	August 18- November 18	500	No prioritization system at this stage	30 alerts
2	30-31 Aug'19	Wageningen	1 Jan '18 – 15 Aug 19	714	1=alert within KBA and protected forest	22 alerts (all positives)
3	25 Sept'19					9 alerts (all positives)
4	19-20 Nov'19	Wageningen	Oct-19	601		27 alerts(all positives)
5	Not done yet	Wageningen	01 Jan 2018 to 23 Jan 2020.	to be completed by WUR	to be completed by WUR	Not done yet

Volunteers on the ground, accompanied by experts from Burung and BLI, ground-truthed the alerts received. We tried to capture the following information: is there forest loss? (true/false), what kind of change do you observe? (add comments in free text box) (see Figures 22 and 23).

Figure 22: Example of a positive alert. A patch of forest was cut down to grow vegetables for the local community. Despite being within the KBA and protected area boundary, the locals had reached an agreement with the local authorities to do this.

Figure 23: Example of a positive alert. Remote sensing experts detected forest loss in this specific area. Volunteers on the ground confirmed a landslide had taken place weeks ago after heavy rainfall. 8 people died. Cutting of trees in the surrounding areas is one of the causes for these terrible landslides.

7 Uptake and performance measures

Table 4 contains performance measures related to the mobile and web app. These values are expected to increase with the planned 2020 nation-wide monitoring campaign in Spain.

Table 4: Performance measures

Description	Value
Number of installs (Android)	143
Number of installs (IOS)	68
Number of web-app users	172
Number of threats	580+

8 Dissemination activities

In Spain, SEO/BirdLife has promoted LandSense activities via:

- The SEO/BirdLife bulletin (Figures 24 to 26)
- Life Followers: <https://followers.seo.org/en/>. The main goal of this project is to increase awareness of the Natura 2000 Network and raise awareness of conservation through involvement of a minimum of 300 young volunteers from the ESC.
- Spanish National Ornithological Congress
- Video tutorials
- The results from the Bird Monitoring Programs and IBA reports are sent yearly to volunteers by email.

Figure 24: LandSense article in SEO/BirdLife bulletin (2016)

Figure 25: LandSense article in SEO/BirdLife bulletin (2017)

Registra amenazas:
En la APP
NATURA ALERT

En la web:

Registra las aves:
En la APP
Programas de seguimiento de SEO/BirdLife

AREAS IMPORTANTES PARA LA CONSERVACIÓN DE LAS AVES Y LA BIODIVERSIDAD

Octavia Infante
SEO/BirdLife

- El trabajo se organiza a través de encargados de una o varias IBA.
- Identifican amenazas y las comunican a los técnicos de campo.
- Actualizan la información ornitológica del área.
- Desarrollan los programas de seguimiento de aves comunes dentro de su espacio según sus posibilidades.

El programa IBA tiene como objetivo identificar y proteger una red de espacios críticos para la biodiversidad a largo plazo de las poblaciones de aves silvestres. Las IBA son espacios de importancia para la conservación de la biodiversidad ornitológica, integrando valores científicos, académicos, objetivos, cuantitativos y cualitativos, y son reconocidos y oficialmente reconocidos por todos los países de BirdLife International.

El seguimiento de avistas de conservación de estos espacios es fundamental para su conservación, ya que funcionan como alerta temprana para la detección de las amenazas. Tanto en su fauna como en su hábitat, la identificación previa de las amenazas es la principal función de los encargados de área. Estas alertas permiten una reacción rápida ante las posibles amenazas evitando hechos consumados.

Para la actualización de la información sobre avistas en las IBA se utilizan habitualmente los inventarios de especies protegidas que dependen de los propios

comunalidades autónomas, aunque los datos aportados por los encargados de área muchas veces completan esa información, especialmente para aquellas especies que, aunque las comunidades tienen obligación de realizar seguimiento, muchas veces no lo hacen. Pero además del conocimiento de la situación de las aves que hacen calificar al espacio como lugar de especial importancia se necesitan realizar un especial esfuerzo por el encargado de cada IBA para tener el inventario de aves completo de ese espacio y, si es posible, su seguimiento. Esta también es una parte importante para calcular la importancia comparativa de cada área.

Para este segundo caso, se hace especial esfuerzo desde SEO/BirdLife de forma que cada encargado de IBA participe en los programas de seguimiento de aves de la organización dentro de los límites de la IBA de la que es responsable.

Este trabajo no solo permite tener una información general de las aves

que ocupan el espacio protegido o a proteger, si no que contribuye a combatir la erosión de las áreas comunes en cada espacio y en el conjunto de las IBA. Además, también se consigue obtener la comparación de la evolución de este grupo de aves con la tendencia que existe fuera de estos espacios. El programa 'Sacro' más facilitará esta información para las aves en época reproductora, el programa 'Sacro' para las aves invernantes y el programa 'Nictus' para las aves migratorias.

Una de las encargadas de IBA visita el foco de seguimiento en el espacio del que es responsable (Alcornoque de Alcalá, IBA 007). Se trata de un área relativamente pequeña donde participa, además de como encargada de IBA, colaborando en los programas Sacro, Sacro-Nictus. Los programas de seguimiento de aves comunes (Sacro, Sacro-Nictus) les permite muy cómodamente a través de la aplicación móvil de los programas de seguimiento de SEO/BirdLife.

La implementación de los encargados de IBA en los programas de seguimiento de aves comunes tiene como objetivo de indicadores generales del estado de la biodiversidad.

Esta IBA es un área importante situada al este de Madrid, con grandes extensiones de campos de cereales (trigo y cebada), olivales, almeces, olivares, arbolado, etc. Hay zonas de cultivo con tulpas, castaños y otros árboles frutales. Además, dada la proximidad a la ciudad de Madrid existen abundantes jardines y uno de los principales problemas son los movimientos de camiones para su explotación, pues fragmentan los hábitats relictos de aves estancadas. Además, en sus proximidades hay polígonos industriales en crecimiento y núcleos de población importantes, lo que origina molestias de vehículos todo terreno, numerosas actividades de bicicletas, todo terreno e incluso actividad de paramotor (parapente motorizado o motorfly). Además, las principales amenazas a la biodiversidad agrícola las son productos fitosanitarios, pesticidas con hormona sintética, abonos de origen sintético y plaguicidas en venta.

Actualmente hay más de 300 encargados de IBA en España, pero esa cifra sin una contribución importante a la red de encargados puede ayudar a que el inventario que se actualiza periódicamente y que los programas de seguimiento de aves comunes incrementen su cobertura, que es más que necesaria en numerosos regiones de España.

Estaciones Sacro

Estaciones Nictus

- Sacro YK7000 1
- Sacro YK7000 2
- Sacro YK7000 3
- IBA Alcornoque de Alcalá
- Cuadrícula UTM 10x10 km

Un ejemplo: IBA 075 Alcornoque de Alcalá, donde se desarrolla el programa Sacro (1), programa Sacro (2) y programa Nictus (3).

Transferir información de avistas (tradicionalmente a otros sistemas e igualmente, en su caso, libre todo, la posible comunicación de un nuevo seguimiento para Madrid). La IBA cumple criterios para estar incluida en el inventario por su importante población de avistas y avistada pero no está reconocida como ZEPA por ser terreno potencial para un nuevo aeropuerto.

Dentro de este espacio, un voluntario desarrolla una unidad muestral para el programa Sacro (2) (estaciones de muestra), tres unidades muestrales Sacro (3) (estaciones de muestra) y una unidad muestral de Nictus (3) (estaciones de muestra).

Además de ser clave el conocimiento de las especies por las que califica la IBA, la comprensión de la avifauna general y la evolución de sus efectivos, el seguimiento de la IBA se completa con la identificación de

amenazas que aparecen en la misma. Muchas de ellas se pueden observar y registrar a la vez que se hacen los muestreos de primavera de Sacro y Nictus y durante los avistados de invierno de Sacro y Nictus.

A partir de 2018 se pondrá en marcha la aplicación que ya se ha mencionado en otras ocasiones para el registro de amenazas Natura Alert (a las que se denominan localmente como LandSense). Con esta aplicación los encargados de IBA podrán ir registrando directamente sobre el terreno las amenazas que se van observando en el espacio.

La aplicación está diseñada especialmente para el registro de amenazas en IBA, y no solo en España, sino la herramienta de BirdLife International para actualizar las amenazas de estos espacios a escala mundial. Permite registrar en todos los formatos que el seguimiento del

www.seguimientodeaves.org

Desde SEO/BirdLife invitamos a todos los encargados de IBA a participar en los programas de seguimiento de aves comunes dentro de su espacio. No solo nos permite conocer mejor de los contenidos de aves en general y de cada una, también la evolución de sus efectivos y contribuir a mejorar la gestión de las áreas comunes, las cuales solo pueden llegar a clasificarse como especies catalogadas gracias al mayor conocimiento de su estado de trabajo (evolución y tendencia de sus poblaciones).

natura-alert.net

En cuanto se ponga en marcha la aplicación Natura Alert comenzará una nueva campaña de actualización de IBA de España, desde esta campaña registrada en el momento de su identificación las coordenadas, las fotos y todos los observaciones que cada encargado de IBA registre.

La información en: www.seguimientodeaves.org y natura-alert.net y para para más detalles contactar con el correo electrónico info@seguimientodeaves.org.

estado de conservación de las IBA exige de cada una de las amenazas: tipo de amenaza y la presión de la misma, que se conoce del momento, el alcance y su severidad. Además registrará la coordenada de forma automática de cada población identificada y permitirá obtener y enviar fotografías y videos, a la vez que se irá registrando el resto de información.

Más información en: www.iasa.org/IBA

Figure 26: LandSense article in SEO/BirdLife bulletin (2018)

In Indonesia, the visibility of the LandSense project is being ensured through stories that are shared through Burung Indonesia's social media, such as Instagram and Facebook. Burung Indonesia has 10,800 followers in Instagram and 16, 701 followers in Facebook that are giving good engagement to the stories. Our Instagram is targeting Indonesian urban youth and our Facebook is targeting our loyal supporters in Indonesia. The highest engagements were found in Instagram, with 477 likes and 10 comments on a post about Local Community Groups that consist of 80% women who conducted monitoring in Golo Damu village.

Below are three stories that have been disseminated using different social media outlets.

Story 1: The consultation with village authorities in four target villages to incorporate community-based monitoring into the Village Development Plan

Figures 27 show examples of this village consultation via facebook and Instagram.

Figure 27: Facebook & Instagram posts about consultation in four target villages

Story 2: Community-based monitoring in Golo Damu village conducted by women LCG

Figure 28 show examples of community-based monitoring shared via facebook and Instagram.

Figure 28: Facebook & Instagram posts about community-based monitoring in Golo Damu village

Story 3: Validating remote sensing alerts on the ground

Figures 29 show examples of validating remote sensing alerts on the ground, disseminated via Twitter.

Figure 29: Twitter posts from the Indonesia validation campaigns

In the upcoming months, the achievements from LandSense will be disseminated via the Community and Village Empowerment Agency’s website, as the head of the agency is willing to provide the space. A further discussion with the agency is also needed to synchronise the data from monitoring activities with the technology-based village profile to demonstrate how the data can be utilized as advocacy material for the agency at a higher level.

9 Challenges

Throughout this forest and habitat monitoring pilot, we have encountered several challenges as outlined below:

- Engaging volunteers & keeping their motivation while the technology is still under development. For example, we could not launch a national scale campaign in 2018 and 2019 because the mobile app and the web app were still being developed. The risk of losing volunteer interest and attention was too high in the past, but we are now better positioned to launch the campaign in the spring of 2020.
- Addressing privacy and traceability (e.g., if SEO/BirdLife wants to follow up on some of the threats reported, they need to know who the person is and have access to their email or phone number to contact them). We have modified the app so that email addresses are collected, which is outlined in the privacy policy associated with the use of Natura Alert so that users know what information is being collected about them and for what purpose.
- Defining the added-value we could offer to citizens, particularly for local communities in Indonesia.
- Organizations willing to join Natura Alert must have an internal user database where they identify volunteers, their role and including their responsible IBA/KBA. As Spain had this database already, we could link them to the Natura Alert backend using the Identity provider system developed by Secure Dimensions. However, this is not the case with Burung. As they do not have an internal user database, we cannot link them to the Natura Alert system and therefore they cannot log in to manage their own data (revise the observations, validate them, download the data, etc). IIASA is trying to find a solution for this technical issue, which can prevent other BirdLife partners from engaging with the existing Natura Alert tools.
- Showing the names of the N2000 sites and IBAs & KBAs in the maps in the web app and mobile app.

10 Next steps

There are several next steps planned for 2020, which include the following:

- BLI and IIASA are planning a face-to-face meeting that will take place before Spring 2020 to discuss important topics including:
 - Pending technical issues
 - The Natura Alert migration to BLI systems
 - Integrating login accounts from other partners
 - Fundraising opportunities post-2020.
- BLI, IIASA and SEO are planning the launch of a data collection campaign at national scale in Spain (Spring 2020), with the aim of producing a national assessment on the Conservation status of Spanish IBAs. The information obtained could be used in the 'IBAs in Danger Initiative 2020', which is a BirdLife initiative launched in 2013 to compile and publish the list of the most threatened IBAs around the world, identified by BirdLife Partners on the basis of monitoring data. <https://birdlife.maps.arcgis.com/apps/Cascade/index.html?appid=29852f78dcd84de3adf5fed4f16465fb>
- Presentation of the Natura Alert demo case at the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) Conference in Trieste, Italy, in September 2020.